

CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIVEMENT

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

NEW INNOVATION IN NATIONAL EDUCATION
FOR ACTIVELY PARTICIPATING IN THE JOURNAL

Axmatova Aziza Hikmat qizi

FRANSUZ TILINING DIPLOMATIK SOHADA TUTGAN O'RNIFRANSIYA-O'ZBEKISTON

MUNOSABATLARI VA UNING TA'LIM TIZIMIGA TA'SIRI

WILL BE AWARDED FOR THEIR PARTICIPATION IN THE ARTICLE

